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1. Science instruments selection and setup

Work package 9 of the LEAPS-INNOV project (GA 101004728) focuses on expanding the existing collaborations of the LEAPS partners towards areas of excellent science as applied to innovation and societal needs. Among the objectives envisioned to achieve this ambitious goal, it was foreseen to “launch a small number of co-creation implementation studies addressing technology challenges collaboratively”. Task 9.2, Co-creation implementation studies developing science instruments to approach sustainable development goals in the context of HE missions, has thus been implemented through an arrangement of an open call and selection of three instrument pilots (also referred to as “implementation studies”).

Information about the Call for proposals and subsequent results have been made available on the LEAPS-INNOV webpage (<https://www.leaps-innov.eu/wp9-call>).

Details about the Call process management and corresponding documents are shown below in Annex I (Approach for the call for proposals in LEAPS-INNOV WP9).

2. Co-creation science instrument pilots result and recommendations

In total 10 proposals for projects with the following distribution in project types have been submitted during the open call for proposals: 9 for the technology developments, and 1 proposal for a development of targeted challenge driven access mode. The top ranked projects selected for funding and implementation were as follows: EASYBRAGG (technology development), STRAQTECH (access mode development) and AFX (technology development).

2.1. Pilots overview summary

EASYBRAGG

Implementation of user-friendly 3D Bragg ptychography at synchrotron sources

Main Applicant: Virginie Chamard, Fresnel CNRS-AMU

Project Partners: ESRF, Diamond, MAX IV

Project Public Summary:

In the recent years, 3D Bragg ptychography (3DBP) has emerged as a powerful crystalline microscopy method, owing to its capability to produce 3D maps of crystalline materials down to 10 nm spatial resolution. As 3DBP is compatible with the investigation of extended, rather complex crystals, it fills the gap between electron microscopy and Bragg coherent diffraction imaging, opening exciting perspectives to a large scientific community, as demonstrated with striking results obtained in physics, nanoscience, materials sciences, and biology. While 3DBP has been performed at various beamlines and several synchrotrons worldwide, some experimental difficulties have prevented its spread towards a larger number of less-experienced synchrotron users. With the advent of 4th generation synchrotron sources, we have shown that a full dataset could be acquired on the minute time scale under relaxed set-up stability requirements, thus tearing down the major barriers for its widespread application. There is now a timely opportunity to gather efforts to allow a large community of users to exploit this microscopy method. To this aim, the EASYBRAGG project proposes to produce a user-friendly BP framework to be implemented at 3rd and 4th generation synchrotron sources.

The EASYBRAGG consortium, composed by Institut Fresnel, ESRF, Diamond and MAX IV, merges recognized experts in 3DBP, including advanced experimental (nanoprobe, scanning) and numerical (inversion codes, methodological developments) aspects. A comprehensive user-friendly (open source) 3DBP package will be produced and implemented at ESRF, Diamond and MAX IV. It will come along with training tutorials and a series of written and oral communications to prospect and identify potential users from other scientific fields. With this collaborative technology development, 3DBP will become available for a large community of users. This will enrich the portfolio of accessible crystalline

microscopy methods and allow scientists to address novel classes of crystalline materials-based phenomena.

STRAQTECH

Strategic access for quantum technology

Main Applicant: apl. Prof. Oliver Rader, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie

Project Partners: SOLEIL, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

Project Public Summary:

Quantum technology is at present developing rapidly and can provide enormous benefit for Europe's society and economy. The applicants have identified examples for crucial scientific questions where synchrotron and FEL radiation can help quantum technology. Currently, access to synchrotron and FEL radiation is granted (i) by each facility individually in the framework of (ii) semester-wise calls and based on (iii) scientific excellence and feasibility criteria which is not ideal for the quantum technology community new to synchrotron and FEL radiation. The present project will in direct interaction with the community identify the most important scientific questions, the resulting ideal way of access, and the required instrumentation. Then one or several access modes will be tested at individual facilities and through LEAPS wide calls. A dedicated scientist will guide the community to existing and newly developed access modes and instrumentation. The project will give perspectives towards new instrumentation and further extension of the project, for example, in the direction of higher TRL levels.

AXF

Acoustofluidic crystallography

Main Applicant: Jonas Sellberg, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Project Partners: DESY, MAX IV

Project Public Summary:

Serial crystallography (SX) has become one of the standard techniques at synchrotrons and x-ray free-electron lasers (XFELs) to obtain (time-resolved) high-resolution structural information from microcrystals of various proteins and enzymes. Nevertheless, reliable sample delivery is often the primary limiting factor in SX. We propose to make use of acoustofluidics in combination with state-of-the-art injection nozzles to reduce sample consumption, enable concentration enrichment in the nozzle and thus avoid clogging. We will use a piezoelectric actuator to create a 2D ultrasonic standing wave perpendicular to the crystal flow, which will focus the crystals into a single line inside a square

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silica capillary that is then integrated in a 3D-printed design for dual flow-focusing nozzles (DFFNs). We name this new modality acoustofluidic crystallography (AFX). The project is divided in 4 work packages with expected deliverables carried out at the partner organizations (KTH, DESY, MAX IV). A post-doctoral researcher would be funded by LEAPS-INNOV and recruited to work full time on the project for 12 months and participate in all work packages onsite. Funding for traveling, equipment and indirect costs has already been acquired elsewhere. The project is expected to: design a prototype for AFX; assemble the final design into a fully functioning device using 3D printing capabilities; install the optimized AFX device at an SX beamline; use the AFX device to perform protein crystallography and thus benchmark the device. The final implementation of the AFX device would be integrated at beamlines at MAX IV (BioMAX and MicroMAX) and PETRA III (P11) and be made available to users. This would allow for the use of acoustofluidics beyond expert users and lead to better use of SX beamtime, less sample consumption and structure determination of proteins that can only be crystallized in small amounts.

Project results are shown in reports provided by the corresponding project responsible, that have been summarised in Annex II (Instrument pilots summarized reports).

2.2. Overall pilots' results and recommendations

In all projects, reviewers saw strong interdisciplinary collaborations that brought together facility expertise with user-driven developments, resulting in significant technical and scientific achievements. Each initiative has delivered tangible outcomes—whether in the form of software frameworks, prototype devices, or community-building tools—that are already in use or positioned to make a clear impact on their respective scientific fields. Dissemination efforts were noted as a strength, with workshops, tutorials, conference presentations, and highlight articles. Collectively, the projects are viewed as successful pilots that exemplify the potential of co-creation to accelerate innovation, standardization, and long-term adoption of advanced techniques across the LEAPS network.

At the same time, reviewers emphasized that the long-term success of these projects will depend on continued outreach beyond the immediate LEAPS community, including high-profile scientific publications, open access to tools and codes, and active engagement of new or less experienced users. They also highlighted the need for sustained community-building, particularly in fields that are still emerging or more conservative, suggesting bottom-up approaches and the identification of key ambassador groups as effective strategies.

To unlock the full potential of co-creation activities in the common environment of LEAPS and its user communities, future selection processes could evolve from traditional open calls toward more targeted, co-designed events that actively convene stakeholders from across facility departments, academia, and industry. Such collaborative forums would create fertile ground for identifying shared grand challenges, catalyzing fresh ideas, and fostering solutions that transcend disciplinary boundaries.

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By deliberately widening participation and encouraging diverse perspectives, these initiatives could become powerful engines of creativity and innovation, ultimately delivering breakthroughs of greater breadth, depth, and relevance to the scientific and industrial communities alike.

In specific terms, any successor of the LEAPS-INNOV activities under the LEAPS umbrella, e.g. through future technology development projects, could

- Foster interdisciplinary collaboration through structured co-creation formats to align facility expertise with user-driven innovation.
- Evolve from traditional open calls to targeted, co-designed events that actively convene diverse stakeholders.
- Broaden participation and encourage inclusive innovation by engaging early-career researchers and adjacent disciplines through formats like hackathons.

Furthermore, in line with the reviewers' recommendations to pursue follow-up initiatives to the pilot studies, it would be highly valuable to rely on cascade funding opportunities in future EU Calls. Such mechanisms would provide the means to further develop and scale up the proposed ideas, thereby maximising impact and ensuring that tangible, long-term benefits for the user community are effectively realised.

3. Annex I: Approach for the call for proposals in LEAPS-INNOV WP9

3.1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide guidelines for successful co-creation pilots in the call for proposals in the LEAPS-INNOV co-creation programme.

LEAPS-INNOV aims at kick-starting the implementation of the LEAPS Technology Roadmap and, at the same time, at fostering collaboration with European industry through open innovation. WP9 in LEAPS-INNOV focusses on the implementation of new strategies and activities for long-term partnerships between industry and the European accelerator-based light sources, synchrotrons and free-electron lasers, with their tens of thousands of users. Via the LEAPS-INNOV-co-creation programme, experienced as well as new user communities have a chance to develop new concepts, methods and technologies suited to their needs together with LEAPS facilities. The focus lies on joint technological developments, advanced research capabilities and access opportunities at the LEAPS facilities for both industry (as collaborator, supplier and user) and academic user communities in general.

3.2. Project types of interest

- a) Technology developments – any development of instrumentation that improves the use of LEAPS facilities for specific user communities. Project deliverables shall be stated clearly in the application and can preferably be a prototype or a technical design report for a science instrument with an instrument / method paper submitted to an open journal. The funding from LEAPS-INNOV can be used for salaries, services or goods as well for collaboration meetings. A clear user commitment (in form of matching funds or complementary resources) is expected.
- b) Development of targeted challenge driven access modes - any development of targeted challenge driven access modes that benefit specific user communities solving a certain problem related to societal challenges at LEAPS facilities that need a collective effort. Targeted challenge driven (strategic) access for well-defined user communities is a cornerstone of the LEAPS strategy of a co-creation approach between facilities, academic research, and innovation driven enterprises. Project deliverables should include a description of the addressed user community, how the user community will organize itself around the strategic access, selection process and criteria for the beam time access, amount of beamtime requested, methods/instrumentation and installations needed. The funding from LEAPS-INNOV can be used for salaries, or services as well as for collaboration meetings. In-kind contribution as additional commitment (in form of matching funds or complementary resources) is expected.

3.3. Funding and eligibility

Funding will be provided to projects for the period 1st January 2023 to 30th June 2024 (the period may be adapted according to the selection process duration). Two or three projects with a budget of 100

to 150 k€ will be funded. In-kind contributions or user-commitment in form of matching funds is expected. An overview and break down of the budget as well as the in-kind contributions foreseen need to be provided with the application.

Eligible are consortia comprising at least two LEAPS-INNOV members and at least one user institution (academic or industrial) representing a larger user community or a user consortium, which is independent (different legal entity) from the LEAPS members. As user institution qualifies any institution that performs research at a LEAPS light source or intends to do so. The application must clearly outline the role of each partner. (In case of industrial partners, they cannot contribute as equipment provider; their contribution should imply active contribution to project development.)

One of the partners (not necessarily the LEAPS-INNOV partners) will have to be the lead applicant and will be responsible for the project management and the budget.

The deliverables should include channels to guarantee a sufficient public dissemination of the project results. Open sharing of project information and deliverables is encouraged among all applicants.

3.4. Selection criteria and process

The criteria for selecting the project include:

- Complementary of the consortia partners, contribution of the user institution
- Benefit for a larger part of the user community
- Alignment with the [LEAPS strategy](#)
- Contribution to LEAPS efforts to link to EU Horizon Europe missions and/or EU partnerships

The selection process will start after the deadline for application with an eligibility check of all proposals by 5th December 2022. Subsequently, the first evaluation will take place on an individual basis by a selection committee comprising of experts of LEAPS working groups, the Executive Board and the Governing Board of LEAPS-INNOV until 11th January 2023 *using the defined evaluation template*. The assignment of the reviewers to the proposals will be based on their expertise and avoiding to include representatives of the institutions involved in the project. This way any conflict of interest is to be avoided. Based on the individual review by the selection committee, the proposals will be ranked. The draft ranking list based on individual grades will be provided to the Review Committee for a final ranking to be confirmed by the Governing Board in a meeting (date to TBD). The Governing Board will be asked to agree on granted projects based on the input from the Review Committee via email or meeting.

The successful proposals will be informed by the WP9 by end January 2023. At the same time, proposers will be informed when their proposal was not successful. A public summary report of the review, comprising an account of the call, its evaluation and its results (including dates of call, how it was published, dates of evaluation, number of proposals received, number of proposals funded, as well as a list of all selected proposers and their funding amounts) will be compiled and published.

- Call opening: 15th October 2022
- Call deadline: 30th November 2022
- Decision on granted proposals: end of January 2023
- Project start: 1st March 2023

3.5. Funding Rules

Participating to LEAPS-INNOV co-creation programme involves accepting all the deadlines and rules as they are described in this document and in other documents referenced. LEAPS-INNOV, in accordance with general principles of fairness, impartiality and transparency, reserves the right to add, change or modify, cancel or amend all or any part of the rules as it deems fit and without notice. It is responsibility of the submitting/successful party to remain informed. In case of any dispute it will be the LEAPS-INNOV Governing Board to emit the final decision.

The LEAPS-INNOV co-creation pilots are, as described, only eligible if at least two LEAPS members and one user/industrial partner is participating in the project. H2020 eligibility rules apply to the co-creation pilot projects as well. Beneficiaries must also ensure the right of controls for the Commission, OLAF and the Court of Auditor and the right for the Commission to make an evaluation of the impact of the action.

The action (LEAPS-INNOV) has to be promoted by the co-creation pilot in all dissemination activities and visibility needs to be given to the EU funding by including the emblem and the funding statement:

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A report towards LEAPS-INNOV WP9 on the finances, activities and outcomes of the co-creation pilots are expected at the end of the project. Project deliverables may vary between a technical design report, detailed design drawings or ideally working prototypes for a science instrument and a description of the developed access mode (addressing user community, how the user community will organize itself around the strategic access, selection process and criteria for beam time access, amount of beamtime requested, methods/instrumentation, installations needed) depending on the type of project. The deliverables, as stated in the application, need to be demonstrated.

The awarded projects duration should end by October 2024 and cannot exceed the duration of the LEAPS-INNOV project, which is scheduled end of March 2025.

3.6. Financial strategy for successful proposals

Funding will be transferred to the successful projects by the coordinator, DESY, holding the budget for the WP9 co-creation call. Depending on the structure and composition of the project consortia, the distribution of the budget will vary.

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In general, LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries will receive the budget for the co-creation pilots in form of a budget transfer in the LEAPS-INNOV project. In comparison, external co-creation partners will receive the budget via sub-contracting.

In case the LEAPS-INNOV beneficiary is lead of the co-creation pilot, the lead can claim the budget for itself and for all external partners at the end of the Reporting Period (as for the rest of expenses within the LEAPS-INNOV project – reimbursement of costs). The lead will have to transfer the money to the external partners by sub-contract or a purchase of services. Partners that are LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries as well receive their budget via a budget transfer from the coordinator directly.

In case, an external partner is lead of the co-creation pilot, the lead and all other external partners receive their budget from the coordinator via subcontracting (or purchase of services) from one of the LEAPS-INNOV partners involved. LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries involved in the project receive their budget via a budget transfer for themselves.

In all subcontracting agreements, a clause should be included clarifying that the budget transfer to the external party will be divided in two steps: an initial transfer of 80% of total budget will be transferred within one month since the official beginning of the project and the remaining 20% will be transferred upon completion of deliverables (to be defined in detail). LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries will have to report the use of budget within the co-creation pilots directly to the European Commission. The subcontracts for external partners will include a budget and task breakdown for the external partners, which these have to adhere to. The LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries are responsible for the proper use of the funding by external partners. The subcontracted partners should report the use of budget to the co-creation pilot lead or the LEAPS-INNOV partner subcontracting them.

4. Annex II: Instrument pilots summarized reports

The paragraphs below reflect, in a summarized fashion, the content of individual project reports provided by the corresponding project responsible.

4.1. EASYBRAGG

The EasyBragg project produced an user-friendly Bragg Ptychography framework suitable for implementation at 3rd and 4th generation synchrotron sources. The code was installed at several beamlines (at ESRF, Diamond and MAX IV), where demonstration experiments were performed using test samples designed for quantifying the performance of the method. Fully successful results were obtained at ID01-ESRF and NanoMAX-MAX IV and should be obtained at ID13-ESRF and I13-Diamond in the following months. In parallel, test samples were produced and distributed to future interested users (at synchrotrons or academic research institutes), several tutorial lectures were given at thematic schools and dissemination of the method was ensured by a series oral communications at international conferences.

The main objective of the EasyBragg project has been reached as the ID01-ESRF beamline is now welcoming Bragg ptychography users. A dedicated technical workshop is scheduled in September 2025 in Marseille, with the possibility to welcome 20 attendees.

The Fresnel Partner took care of transferring the initial code to the computing engineer and followed its development in Python and its implementation at synchrotrons. In addition, Fresnel designed the test samples, produced the test samples and took part in the four test experiments at synchrotrons. Fresnel also took part in the data analysis, with the objectives of solving the remaining issues for on line analysis, in particular at ID01-ESRF. Fresnel also delivered several talks at conferences promoting the method and produced several tutorials, delivered in Cargese Coherex thematic school in 10/2023 and at the XTOP conference in Carry-le-Rouet in March 2024. Fresnel is now organising a dedicated technical workshop (including defining the scientific content and delivering lectures) to be held in September 2025 in Marseille.

The ESRF Partner took care of the implementation of the produced Python code at ESRF and MAX IV and its incorporation into the code suites of the ESRF data analysis group, in view of its maintenance. ESRF has ensured the implementation of the code at the ID01 and ID13 beamlines and has also leaded the two demonstration experiments. Data analysis is on the way to evaluate the performances of the method. ID01 is now able to welcome Bragg ptychography users and to ensure online analysis of the data. An introductory tutorial of the new tool was performed at the 2025 ESRF meeting. ESRF is also strongly involved in the production the code documentation, the technical article and the EasyBragg workshop in September 2025, for which they work with Fresnel on the definition of the scientific content and the different lectures (including practical exercise on computers).

The MAX IV Partner took care of the implementation of the Python code at Max IV together with ESRF. MAX IV has also led the demonstration experiment at Nanomax and is now involved in the data analysis. MAX IV has delivered several talks at international conferences to promote the method and is now involved in the organisation of the ptychography workshop.

The Diamond Partner took care of the implementation of the Python code at Diamond. Diamond has also led the demonstration experiment at Diamond and was involved in the purchase of the test samples, distributed to future Bragg ptychography users.

4.2. STRAQTECH

Interviews with experts on access modes and a Mini-Workshop with researchers advanced understanding of the boundary conditions of LEAPS sources and quantum technology researchers' needs for synchrotron radiation access. Conservative preferences for access modes and limited quantum researcher participation (1:3 relative to synchrotron staff) highlighted the need for broader outreach and practical examples. Proactive attendance at quantum technology conferences has been initiated, supported by the first edition of the Hitchhikers' Guide to Synchrotron and FEL Light Sources for Quantum Technology distributed at EQTC 2024 with link to a new mailing list. A pilot call was initiated at BESSY II with 2 proposals selected. Key next steps include publishing the Guide's updated edition, submitting an invited perspective article to *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, and proposing a dedicated EQTC 2025 session. Progress aligns with timelines, driving innovation and user benefits.

The expertise across the consortium is broad. K. Temst, based at KU Leuven and imec, brings strong links to semiconductor technology and extensive experience with managing access to large-scale analytical tools, also on a European level. J. Daillant and the team at SOLEIL have a long-standing track record in user programs and research on quantum materials. He has recently moved to the ESRF, which stands out as a pioneering European synchrotron facility offering targeted access programs. At HZB, O. Rader operates instruments at a synchrotron source comparable to SOLEIL and is also actively engaged in the Helmholtz Research Field "Information" which spans topics from quantum materials to quantum technology.

O. Rader, A. Makarova (HZB) and K. Temst (Leuven) worked together on the review article to be published in *Adv. Funct. Mater.* O. Rader, A. Makarova, M. Krivenkov (HZB), K. Temst, and J. Daillant (Soleil/ESRF) jointly organized the online Mini-Workshop "Synchrotron and FEL radiation for quantum technology" on 4 Oct 2023. F. Fraissard (Soleil) provided input for the workshop. On 28 Oct 2024, K. Temst hosted a meeting at Leuven on the development of strategic access for quantum and information technology attended by O. Rader, P. van der Heide (imec Leuven), K. Attenkofer, and S. Parkin (the latter online). A. Taleb-Ibrahimi and J.-P. Rueff (both Soleil) help preparing the final workshop in June 2025 for a follow-up project.

4.3. AFX

The project has successfully achieved all planned objectives, with all tasks, deliverables, and milestones completed as promised. The developed AFX sample delivery device has demonstrated its innovation potential by significantly enhancing the indexing yield of protein crystals, making it highly beneficial for experiments where sample availability is limited. This advancement enables a more efficient and cost-effective approach to serial crystallography, reducing sample wastage while improving data quality. Additionally, the seamless integration with the beamline has ensured stable and reproducible sample delivery, addressing key challenges in microfluidic-based delivery methods. The outcomes contribute to advancing serial crystallography, offering a more efficient, reproducible, and cost-effective method for the user community, with potential applications in structural biology and pharmaceutical research.

The project benefited significantly from the complementary expertise of partners MAX IV and CFEL. Both facilities contributed to experimental planning and execution by delivering high-quality protein samples, supporting beamtime operations with essential equipment, and assisting in beamline setup. Both teams collaborated closely with us on the design and integration of the sample delivery adapter, ensuring compatibility with synchrotron conditions. During beamtime, they facilitated data collection and performed the data processing to derive protein structures. Their in-depth knowledge of crystallography, instrumentation, and data analysis was crucial in maximizing the impact of the project and achieving meaningful scientific outcomes.

